

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

In this article, there are opinions about the appropriate use of modern technologies and its importance in the process of teaching English. It also talks about the methods of using technological tools in learning foreign languages.

INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH

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ABSTRACT

Mazkur maqolada Ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida zamonaviy texnologiyalardan o'rinli foydalanish va uning ahamiyati haqida fikr-mulohazalar yuritiladi. Shuningdek, chet tillarini o'rganishda texnologik vositalardan foydalanishning uslublari haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Introduction:

The new era imposes new tasks and several responsibilities on the teachers of today. With the introduction of modern technology, the tradition of teaching English has changed significantly. Resolution No. 34 dated January 19, 2022, "On additional measures to improve the learning of foreign languages" by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

the decision was made¹. According to this decision, foreign language teachers were assigned the responsibility of introducing advanced methods of teaching using modern pedagogic and information communication technologies and preparing the growing young generation to be able to speak foreign languages freely. The decision consists of several paragraphs, and the ninth paragraph of the decision describes in detail the use of innovative technologies.

Today, the number of languages spoken in the world is about 600. They develop from each other and can form unique family trees. Among them, English is one of the languages belonging to the German language family. One of the urgent issues of the present time is the teaching of foreign languages as a second language and universal human values such as love for the motherland, loyalty, high pride, and national pride in the young generation. is to educate in the spirit. For the last 2-3 years, in our country, it is necessary to attract the young generation to learn English and to obtain B1 or C1 level certificates and ILTIES diplomas. The goal is for all the future generations of our Motherland to learn foreign languages as if they were our mother tongue, to master the modern technologies of the developing world without any obstacles. And besides, in the 21st century, when information communication is developing, the introduction of new words, terms and expressions from one language to another has become a natural state. This situation, together with the enrichment and development of the language, sheds light on such features as the ability to replace incoming new words with the corresponding word or word in the Uzbek language or to find an alternative meaning.

According to the ninth paragraph of the decision, The National Broadcasting Company of Uzbekistan, the State Committee for Communication, Informatization and Telecommunication Technologies, the Press and Information Agency of Uzbekistan and the National Information Agency of Uzbekistan, taking into account the interests and interests of children and youth provide the following:

Preparation and broadcasting of programs on teaching foreign languages to children and teenagers on television, including through local TV channels, scientific and popular, foreign artistic and cultural programs dedicated to the history and culture of other nations, world science and technology. regularly showing multiplex films with Uzbek subtitles; Significantly increasing the access of educational institutions to international sources of education and knowledge through the "ZiyoNet" network, enriching its resource center with multimedia resources, applications for personal computers and mobile devices, as well as educational and fiction literature in English, publishing newspapers and magazines decorated with specialized pictures, organizing special columns and applications for them", all English language teachers at this moment began to feel the need to use technology in order to enliven their lessons.

Nowadays, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is much higher than before. A number of English language experts are implementing new methods and ways of learning English. This will definitely increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages.

Teaching using technology has several unique advantages. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep up with the times and move forward.

¹ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 34 dated 19.01.2022

Technology is gradually replacing traditional education. Today, a number of new programs and shows that help to teach English are regularly broadcasted on television programs.

It should also be noted that today new methods of using modern innovative technologies have been introduced in Uzbekistan to increase the effectiveness of teaching. For example, a student who is being taught a foreign language on the basis of multimedia has the opportunity to develop four skills and learn both by seeing and listening through interesting materials. In addition, the student can guess the meaning of some words by watching live actions and tries to understand it.

The fact that some teachers do not know how to apply and do not use technologies during English lessons leads to some boredom of students. It is for this reason, that is, in order not to extinguish the enthusiasm of the learner, the use of technologies and at least the computer during the lesson ensures that the learner's interest increases. After all, educational materials prepared according to the learner's age, interest, ability, mastery of the lessons will definitely be effective. On the contrary, if we teachers do not choose educational materials based on these requirements, if we broadcast video films, songs or texts containing complex words to elementary school students or show them through multimedia and computers, when we show educational materials consisting of very simple texts to students of middle and high classes or groups, the students' interest in learning the language gradually fades and they do not master the lessons. This, in turn, can lead to a decrease in grades and a loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students. So, it follows that the main task is not only to use technologies during the lesson, but to be able to use them in their place and to ensure that the use of technologies serves to increase the student's knowledge.

According to the requirements of the current CEFR, i.e. the International European Education Standards, four competences: (*writing, reading, listening, speaking*) are conducted in English. It is important to use technology effectively and appropriately during lessons. For example, listening comprehension lessons have their own rules for playing audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the learner to understand the audio material he is listening to and to be able to analyze it without difficulty. For this, first of all, it is necessary to prepare the environment for playing the audio material, in which the listeners should ensure a calm environment, and the teacher should pay attention to the quality of the audio being played and the sound amplifiers working well, and the exercises to be performed before and after the audio is played. It should be ready and students should be provided with handouts. After all the requirements are met, the teacher can start broadcasting the audio material to the students. Listening is performed at least twice, otherwise language learners may not understand the topic and may not be able to perform the exercises correctly after listening to the audio material.

Conclusion:

It is also a very effective way to show students videos - movies, clips, and discuss them using multimedia in the process of teaching using technology in speaking and writing. It is possible to use the vocabulary familiar to the students, to explain the words if there are new and complex words, and after completing the exercises related to the new words, it is possible to show the video material. . In order to carry out this process, it is important to have a quiet,

noise-free environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, an opportunity for everyone to watch, and to check that the loudspeakers are working. Before releasing the video, the students should discuss the topic of the video to be shown, hold a question and answer session, and then release the video material after making sure that the students are really interested in this topic. When the video is over, the teacher should be interested in the students' thoughts about the video and do exercises. When these stages are carried out correctly, these lessons will definitely contribute to the increase of students' interest and knowledge. It follows from this that the role of modern technologies in enriching our lessons, interesting students and enriching their knowledge is incomparable. Being able to use them correctly and appropriately is the main guarantee of our success.

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